

Combined electrification and carbon capture for low-carbon cement: techno-economic assessment of different designs

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Supplementary Material

The Supplementary Material comprises 51 pages, structured as follows:

- Section 1 provides additional information for estimating the thermodynamic properties of the simulated solid species.
- Section 2 details the modelling approach for each subsystem of the reference cement plant, including model assumptions, results, and validation.
- Section 3 covers the quality specifications for the captured CO₂ considered in this study, along with the modelling of the CO₂ compression and purification unit (CPU).
- Section 4 outlines the key assumptions in designing the low-carbon cement plant configurations examined and provides details on the main process streams for each case.
- Section 5 presents a comprehensive overview of the cost correlations, installation factors, and process contingencies used for the economic analysis.
- Section 6 evaluates the impact of carbon tax on the cost of clinker (*COC*) for both the reference plant and the low-carbon configurations.

1. Thermodynamic properties of solid components

The computation of energy balances in the process simulations reported in the main text requires the evaluation of enthalpy properties for numerous solid species, which are not included in the gPROMS Process 2023.2.0 software database (Siemens, 2024). Enthalpy at a generic temperature can be computed once the enthalpy of formation in standard conditions ($H_{f,i}^0$) is known (Table S1) and the heat capacity ($c_{P,i}$) is appropriately estimated for each species.

Table S1. Enthalpy of formation of solid species simulated.

Species	$H_{f,i}^0$ (J/mol)	Reference
CaCO ₃	-1206920	Siemens (2024)
SiO ₂	-910700	Mcbride et al. (2002)
Al ₂ O ₃	-1675700	Siemens (2024)
Fe ₂ O ₃	-825500	Siemens (2024)
MgCO ₃	-1096000	Mcbride et al. (2002)
CaO	-635090	Siemens (2024)
MgO	-601241	Siemens (2024)
(CaO) ₂ ·SiO ₂ (C ₂ S)	-2306697	Hanein et al. (2020)
(CaO) ₃ ·SiO ₂ (C ₃ S)	-2933130	Hanein et al. (2020)
(CaO) ₃ ·Al ₂ O ₃ (C ₃ A)	-3587800	Hanein et al. (2020)
(CaO) ₄ ·Al ₂ O ₃ ·Fe ₂ O ₃ (C ₄ AF)	-5076016	Hanein et al. (2020)
CaO·Al ₂ O ₃ (CA)	-2326300	Hanein et al. (2020)
(CaO) ₂ ·Fe ₂ O ₃ (C ₂ F)	-2139280	Hanein et al. (2020)

An extensive literature review was conducted to identify available data or correlations for the estimation of heat capacity. Correlations were selected based on the best alignment between their temperature range of validity and the temperature range of the cement production process. Preference was given to correlations that did not exhibit divergence outside their range of validity.

Once suitable data or correlations were selected, they were used to estimate the regression coefficients of the polynomial expression utilised by gPROMS Process 2023.2.0 (Siemens, 2024) for heat capacity calculations, as shown in Equation 1:

$$c_{P,i} = C_0 + C_1 \cdot T(K) + C_2 \cdot T^2(K) + C_3 \cdot T^3(K) + C_4 \cdot T^4(K). \quad (1)$$

In Equation 1, $c_{P,i}$ is the temperature-dependent heat capacity of pure component i , $C_{0,\dots,4}$ are the new regression coefficients for the polynomial expression, and T is the absolute temperature.

The estimated regression coefficients for each solid species, along with the literature source of the original data or correlation and the temperature range of validity, are presented in Table S2.

Table S2. Regression coefficients for the heat capacity correlation employed in gPROMS and temperature range of validity for each solid species in the simulation.

Species	C_0	$C_1 \cdot 10^1$	$C_2 \cdot 10^4$	$C_3 \cdot 10^7$	$C_4 \cdot 10^{11}$	T_{min} (K)	T_{max} (K)	Reference original data or correlation
CaCO ₃	14.8233	3.42005	-4.50967	2.83382	-6.51780	200	1600	Mcbride et al. (2002) (range 200-1600K)
SiO ₂	64.0196	-0.0781564	0.229625	-0.12892	0.267083	270	1800	Mcbride et al. (2002) (range 848-1200K)
Al ₂ O ₃	-0.0363713	3.60099	-3.84913	1.80974	-3.03883	200	2300	Mcbride et al. (2002) (range 200-2300K)
Fe ₂ O ₃	-21.2000	6.28200	-8.41600	4.15800	0	100	1800	Siemens, 2024
MgCO ₃	12.0645	3.16273	-4.16314	3.10854	-8.69591	270	1273	Mcbride et al. (2002) (range 500-1263K)
CaO	26.0607	0.819481	-0.97366	0.542169	-1.11624	270	3200	Linstrom and Mallard (2001) (range 298-3200K)
MgO	17.5695	1.00575	-1.19919	0.660972	-1.34775	270	3100	Mcbride et al. (2002) (range 500-3100K)
C ₂ S	63.4408	3.03379	-3.08158	1.54729	-2.99346	200	1800	Hanein et al. (2020)
C ₃ S	86.0963	4.01864	-4.14237	2.08353	-4.03515	200	1800	Haas et al. (1981)
C ₃ A	142.269	3.19321	-2.72094	1.01074	-1.28317	298	1800	Bonnicksen (1955)
C ₄ AF	374.426	0.728016	0	0	0	298	1863	Hanein et al. (2020)
CA	16.6393	5.19038	-6.87829	4.14251	-9.05531	298	1800	Bonnicksen (1955)
C ₂ F	111.245	3.64249	-2.87332	0.258924	3.01096	298	1800	Bonnicksen (1954)

2. Reference cement plant modelling

The approach used to model the reference cement plant is outlined below, covering the sub-models for each unit operation, any necessary custom models, and the key assumptions applied.

The reference plant (Figure S1) represents a modern, efficient clinker production process with a preheater-calciner system. It is modelled using gPROMS Process 2023.2.0 (Siemens, 2024) with steady-state material and energy balances following a modular approach. Complex units within the process (e.g., the rotary kiln) are represented by a series of simpler custom and built-in models, such as mixers, splitters, conversion reactors, and others.

Figure S1. Block flow diagram of the modern, efficient cement production process considered as the reference.

It is worth specifying that throughout the entire study, the air conditions assumed are the ones reported in Table S3.

Table S3. Ambient air conditions assumed in the study.

Variable		Value
Temperature	°C	20
Pressure	bar	1
Molar composition		
O ₂	% mol wet	20.74
N ₂	% mol wet	77.30
CO ₂	% mol wet	0.04
H ₂ O	% mol wet	1.00
Ar	% mol wet	0.92

2.1 Raw mill

The raw mill is the unit in which the wet raw meal is finely milled and dried by the exhaust gas exiting the preheating tower. In this work, the raw mill is modelled as a black box with macroscopic material and energy balances. As represented in Figure S2, the raw mill model includes:

- 3 inlet material streams (wet raw meal, exhaust gas from pyroprocess and false air).
- 2 outlet material streams (dry raw meal and flue gas after drying).

It is assumed thermal equilibrium between the outlet solid and the gas streams, hence they exit the unit at the same temperature.

Figure S2. Scheme of the raw mill model.

Apart from the input stream connection, the input variables of the model are:

- Residual moisture (MR) in the raw meal after drying expressed as mass percentage (wet basis).
- False air ingress (FA^{IN}) expressed as percentage of the mass flowrate of gas entering the mill, used to compute the inlet mass flowrate of false air (\dot{m}_{FA}^{IN}) as:

$$\dot{m}_{FA}^{IN} = FA^{IN}/100 \cdot \dot{m}_G^{IN} \cdot VF_G^{IN} \quad (2)$$

where VF_G^{IN} is the vapor fraction of the gas stream entering the unit.

- Temperature, pressure and molar composition of the false air as provided in Table S3.
- Raw mill oversize (OS) expressed as percentage of the design capacity under nominal conditions for the clinker process. Oversizing the raw mill is necessary because it undergoes frequent maintenance, leading to operation downtime of 10-15% of the pyroprocess runtime.

This affects both the material and energy balances of the system.

The model is composed by Equations 3-13, where \dot{m} , w and H correspond to mass flowrate, mass fraction, and mass enthalpy, respectively. The superscripts “IN” and “OUT” indicate inlet and outlet streams, while the subscripts “S” and “G” refer to solid and gaseous streams, respectively. The total flowrate of each species i (\dot{m}_i^{TOT}) fed to the system is computed by:

$$\dot{m}_i^{TOT} = \dot{m}_S^{IN} \cdot w_{i,S}^{IN} + \dot{m}_G^{IN} \cdot w_{i,G}^{IN} + \dot{m}_{FA}^{IN} \cdot w_{i,FA}^{IN} \quad (3)$$

Since H_2O is the only species that transfers between the solid and the gas stream due to drying, it has a dedicated material balance:

$$w_{\text{H}_2\text{O},S}^{\text{OUT}} = MR/100 \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{m}_G^{\text{OUT}} \cdot w_{\text{H}_2\text{O},G}^{\text{OUT}} = \dot{m}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{TOT}} - \dot{m}_S^{\text{OUT}} \cdot w_{\text{H}_2\text{O},S}^{\text{OUT}} \quad (5)$$

For the generic gaseous species j (with the exception of H_2O) the material balance in the gas and solid phase is determined by:

$$\dot{m}_G^{\text{OUT}} \cdot w_{j,G}^{\text{OUT}} = \dot{m}_j^{\text{TOT}} \quad (6)$$

$$\dot{m}_S^{\text{OUT}} \cdot w_{i,S}^{\text{OUT}} = 0 \quad (7)$$

For the generic solid species k , the material balance in the gas and solid phase is determined by:

$$\dot{m}_G^{\text{OUT}} \cdot w_{k,G}^{\text{OUT}} = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$\dot{m}_S^{\text{OUT}} \cdot w_{k,S}^{\text{OUT}} = \dot{m}_k^{\text{TOT}} \quad (9)$$

The overall material balances are given by:

$$\dot{m}_S^{\text{OUT}} = \dot{m}_S^{\text{OUT}} \cdot w_{\text{H}_2\text{O},S}^{\text{OUT}} + \sum_k \dot{m}_k^{\text{TOT}} \quad (10)$$

$$\dot{m}_S^{\text{IN}} + \dot{m}_G^{\text{IN}} + \dot{m}_{\text{FA}}^{\text{IN}} = \dot{m}_S^{\text{OUT}} + \dot{m}_G^{\text{OUT}} \quad (11)$$

The overall energy balance is given by:

$$\dot{m}_S^{\text{IN}} \cdot H_S^{\text{IN}} + \dot{m}_G^{\text{IN}} \cdot H_G^{\text{IN}} + \dot{m}_{\text{FA}}^{\text{IN}} \cdot H_{\text{FA}}^{\text{IN}} = \dot{m}_S^{\text{OUT}} \cdot H_S^{\text{OUT}} + \dot{m}_G^{\text{OUT}} \cdot H_G^{\text{OUT}} \quad (12)$$

Finally, the real amount of solid raw meal ($\dot{m}_S^{\text{OUT},real}$) sent to the pyroprocess is related to OS trough:

$$\dot{m}_S^{\text{OUT},real} = \frac{\dot{m}_S^{\text{OUT}}}{1 + OS/100} \quad (13)$$

2.2 Preheating tower

The preheating tower of a modern cement plant consists of a series of cyclones connected by risers designed to recover heat from the hot gas exiting the calciner and transfer it to the solid raw materials by direct contact. Each combination of a cyclone and a riser forms a preheating stage, numbered from top to bottom.

At each stage, the solid material from the cyclone above is mixed with the gas coming from the cyclone below inside the riser duct. Within the cyclone, the solids are collected at the bottom and descend into the lower stage, while the gas exits from the top and is directed to the stage above. This is not a perfect separation, as some solids remain entrained in the gas flow; hence, a cyclone is characterised by collection efficiency. Each preheating stage results in a pressure drop and a heat loss. Due to the high temperatures, especially in the lower cyclones, certain reactions can occur, such as the calcination of MgCO_3 and the re-carbonation of CaO to CaCO_3 .

A preheating stage is modelled as a combination of gPROMS built-in models including “Mixer” “Reactor conversion” and “Component splitter”, and a custom “Pressure drop” model (Figure S3).

The model includes:

- 3 inlet material streams (solids from the stage above, dusty gas from the stage below and false air).
- 2 outlet material streams (solids to the stage below and dusty gas to the stage above).

It is assumed that thermal equilibrium is achieved between the solid and gas outlet streams, meaning that they exit at the same temperature.

Figure S3. Block flow diagram of the preheating stage model.

The pressure drop model simply consists in Equations 14-15, accounting for pressure drop across the riser duct and the cyclone. The pressure drop ($p^{OUT} - p^{IN}$) is directly proportional to the density of the heterogeneous gas-solid mixture (ρ_{MIX}) and the square of gas velocity (v_G^{IN}) at the cyclone inlet (Bhatty et al., 2011).

$$p^{OUT} - p^{IN} = -a \cdot \rho_{MIX} \cdot \frac{(v^{IN})^2}{2} \quad (14)$$

In this Equation, v_G^{IN} is related to the inlet cross-sectional area (A^{IN}) of the cyclone through the gas volumetric flowrate (\dot{V}_G^{IN}):

$$v_G^{IN} = \frac{\dot{V}_G^{IN}}{A^{IN}} \quad (15)$$

The model allows for a “design mode” where v_G^{IN} is set and A^{IN} is calculated, or an “operation mode” where A^{IN} is specified for an existing cyclone and the corresponding v_G^{IN} is determined.

Apart from the input stream connection, the input variables of the model are:

- Pressure drop coefficient (a) in Equation 14 to estimate the pressure drop.
- Either v_G^{IN} or A^{IN} depending on the mode selected.
- Heat loss expressed as energy per mass unit of clinker produced, applied in the “Reactor conversion” model.
- Stoichiometry and conversion of reactions in the “Reactor conversion” model, if applicable. Additionally, the reference compound to which the conversion is referred must be specified.
- Cyclone collection efficiency, which defines the split ratio of solid species in the “Component splitter” model.

- False air ingress (FA^{IN}) expressed as percentage of the mass flowrate of gas entering the preheating stage, used to compute the inlet mass flowrate of false air (\dot{m}_{FA}^{IN}) by:

$$\dot{m}_{FA}^{IN} = FA^{IN}/100 \cdot \dot{m}_G^{IN} \cdot VF_G^{IN} \quad (16)$$

where VF_G^{IN} is the vapor fraction of the gas stream entering the unit.

- Temperature, pressure and molar composition of the false air as provided in Table S3.

The lowest cyclone stage, known as the calciner cyclone, is modelled similarly, with the only difference being that there are 2 inlet streams instead of 3: dusty gas from the calciner and false air.

2.3 Solid fuel model

In cement plants, solid fuels such as coal and petcoke are typically burnt to meet the process heat demand. In the transition towards more sustainable cement production, many plants also incorporate waste-derived alternative fuels, which are composed of various carbon-containing solid wastes.

Coal, petcoke, and alternative fuels are complex, heterogeneous mixtures of carbon, organic matter, ash, and moisture, lacking a defined chemical formula. Instead, they are characterised by:

- Proximate analysis, which determines the mass fractions of moisture (M), fixed carbon (FC), volatile matter (VM), and ash.
- Ultimate analysis, which provides the elemental composition, detailing the mass fractions of the elements that make up the fuel.
- Ash composition, reporting the mass fraction of oxides typically contained in the ash.

Within gPROMS, these types of fuels cannot be directly processed using the default “Source Material” model. Therefore, a custom model was developed to translate the data from proximate analysis, ultimate analysis and ash composition into specific chemical species that can be effectively managed by the process simulator.

As represented in Figure S4, the model includes:

- 1 outlet material stream (solid fuel in terms of decomposition species, as explained further below).
- 1 outlet energy stream (accounting for the mismatch between the actual enthalpy of the fuel and that of decomposition species, as explained in the following).

Figure S4. Scheme of the solid fuel model.

The input variables of the model are:

- Temperature (T_{fuel}): the model assumes the fuel is already dried, so this temperature represents the fuel temperature as it enters the process after drying and storage. The required

heat for drying must be accounted for within the entire flowsheet as the heat per unit of fuel that must be supplied.

- Pressure: although solids do not have an associated pressure, 1 bar (ambient conditions) is set as input to calculate thermodynamic properties.
- Total flowrate (\dot{m}_{fuel}).
- Proximate analysis: expressed as the mass fraction (PXA_i) for M on a wet basis [kg/kg_{wet fuel}], and for FC, VM and Ash on a dry basis [kg/kg_{dry fuel}].
- Ultimate analysis: provides the mass fraction (UA_i) of C, H, N, Cl, S, O and Ash in dry basis [kg/kg_{dry fuel}].
- Ash composition: specifies the mass fraction (Ash_i) of SiO₂, Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, CaO and MgO on an ash basis [kg/kg_{ash}].
- Fuel higher heating value (HHV) on a dry basis [kJ_{HHV}/kg_{dry fuel}].

The model (Equations 17-30) assumes that the fuel decomposes into basic “decomposition species” such as C, H₂, N₂, Cl₂, S, O₂, H₂O, SiO₂, Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, CaO and MgO, which can be handled by gPROMS. The mass flowrate ($\dot{m}_{D,i}$) for each decomposition species i is computed by:

$$\dot{m}_{D,i} = \dot{m}_{fuel} \cdot (1 - PXA_M) \cdot UA_i \quad \text{for } i = \text{C, H}_2 \text{ or H, N}_2 \text{ or N, Cl}_2 \text{ or Cl, S, O}_2 \text{ or O} \quad (17)$$

$$\dot{m}_{D,i} = \dot{m}_{fuel} \cdot (1 - PXA_M) \cdot PA_{Ash} \cdot Ash_i \quad \text{for } i = \text{SiO}_2, \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3, \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3, \text{CaO, MgO} \quad (18)$$

$$\dot{m}_{D,H_2O} = \dot{m}_{fuel} \cdot PXA_M \quad (19)$$

The energy balance is represented as:

$$\dot{m}_{fuel} \cdot H_D = \dot{m}_{fuel} \cdot H_{fuel} + \dot{Q}_D \quad (20)$$

where \dot{Q}_D is the decomposition heat and is connected to the outlet energy stream in Figure S4. This term adjusts for the discrepancy between the actual enthalpy of the fuel (H_{fuel}) and the enthalpy of the decomposition species mixture (H_D).

The model computes H_{fuel} in Equation 20 by dividing the fuel into three components: dry ash-free (DAF), moisture (M) and ash, and considers the contribution of each part as:

$$\dot{m}_{fuel} \cdot H_{fuel} = \dot{m}_{DAF} \cdot H_{DAF} + \dot{m}_{Ash} \cdot H_{Ash} + \dot{m}_M \cdot H_M \quad (21)$$

where

$$\dot{m}_{DAF} = \dot{m}_{fuel} \cdot (1 - PXA_M) \cdot (1 - PXA_{Ash}) \quad (22)$$

$$\dot{m}_{Ash} = \dot{m}_{fuel} \cdot (1 - PXA_M) \cdot PXA_{Ash} \quad (23)$$

$$\dot{m}_M = \dot{m}_{fuel} \cdot PXA_M \quad (24)$$

H_{Ash} and H_M in Equation 21 can be computed by gPROMS with a suitable thermodynamic model, since they involve conventional species. On the contrary, H_{DAF} cannot be directly computed and it

requires the determination of the formation enthalpy ($H_{f,DAF}^o$) at 25°C and of the $c_{P,DAF}$ at T_{fuel} . To estimate $H_{f,DAF}^o$, the DAF fuel is represented as a pseudomolecule with the empirical formula $C_1H_{n_H}N_{n_N}Cl_{n_{Cl}}S_{n_S}O_{n_O}$. Stoichiometric coefficients n_i for each element i are calculated by means of the elements molar weight (MW_i):

$$n_i = \frac{UA_i}{UA_C} \cdot \frac{MW_C}{MW_i} \quad \text{for } i = H, N, Cl, S, O \quad (25)$$

The complete combustion reaction of the DAF fuel reported in Equation 26 can be balanced through atomic balances as:

yielding:

$$a = 1, \quad b = \frac{n_H}{2} - n_{Cl}, \quad c = n_{Cl}, \quad d = \frac{n_N}{2}, \quad e = n_S, \quad f = 1 + \frac{b}{2} + e - \frac{n_O}{2} \quad (27)$$

Once the stoichiometric coefficients a , b , c , d , e and f are determined, the mass fractions of the combustion reactants ($w_{REACT,i}^{COMB}$) and products ($w_{PROD,i}^{COMB}$) can be calculated.

The HHV is defined as the amount of heat released by the unit mass of fuel (initially at 25 °C) when it undergoes complete combustion and the combustion products are cooled back down to 25°C. Only the DAF portion of the fuel contributes to combustion, hence Equation 28 applies at 25°C:

$$w_{DAF}^{COMB} \cdot HHV_{DAF} = H_{PROD}^{COMB} - (w_{DAF}^{COMB} \cdot H_{f,DAF}^o + w_{O_2}^{COMB} \cdot H_{f,O_2}^o) \quad (28)$$

where the only unknown is $H_{f,DAF}^o$, as the other enthalpic terms are computed using a suitable thermodynamic model.

The method developed to estimate $H_{f,DAF}^o$ was validated by comparing predicted values for methane, propane, and ethanol against known literature values, as shown in Table S4.

Table S4. Validation of calculation of heat of formation (Linstrom and Mallard, 2001).

Species	Predicted $H_{f,DAF}^o$ (kJ/kg)	Literature $H_{f,DAF}^o$ (kJ/kg)	Relative error (%)
Methane	-4662.9	-4650.0	0.28
Propane	-2300.4	-2374.3	3.12
Ethanol	-5997.9	-5991.0	0.11

The $c_{P,DAF}$ at T_{fuel} is computed employing the generalised Equation for coal proposed by Richardson (1993), valid in the range 300-600 K:

$$c_{P,DAF} = A(T_{fuel}) + B(T_{fuel}) \cdot PXA_{VM}^{DAF} + C(T_{fuel}) \cdot (PXA_{VM}^{DAF})^2 + \frac{D(T_{fuel})}{PXA_{VM}^{DAF} + 0.1} \quad (29)$$

where PXA_{VM}^{DAF} is the VM fraction in DAF terms, while the coefficients A , B , C and D depend on T_{fuel} with the following form:

$$P = P_0 + P_1 \cdot T_{fuel} + P_2 \cdot (T_{fuel})^2 \quad P = A, B, C, D \quad (30)$$

with the values of P_j illustrated in Table S5.

Table S5. Coefficients values associated with Equations 29 and 30 (Richardson, 1993).

Coefficient	$P_0 \cdot 10^1$	$P_1 \cdot 10^3$	$P_2 \cdot 10^6$
A	-5.9430	9.0920	-7.3400
B	17.910	-15.070	19.600
C	-20.700	17.440	-22.093
D	0.2985	-0.52475	0.55370

2.4 Calciner

The calciner of a cement plant is a reactor unit operating at 850-920°C, where the main reaction of CaCO_3 calcination occurs. Heat for this reaction is supplied by burning fuel, aided by hot tertiary air from the clinker cooler and exhaust gases from the rotary kiln.

In addition, mineral phases such as calcium aluminate (CA), dicalcium ferrite (C_2F), and belite (C_2S) begin forming in the calciner. If sulphur is present in the fuel, SO_2 generated during combustion reacts with CaO forming CaSO_4 . These reactions are exothermic and will reduce the energy requirement in the calciner.

The calciner model combines “Mixer” and “Reactor conversion” units in gPROMS (Figure S5) and includes:

- 6 inlet material streams (solids from the stage above, fuel, tertiary air from the clinker cooler, dusty exhaust gas from the kiln, false air and transport air).
- 1 outlet material stream (dusty gas to the calciner cyclone).
- 1 inlet energy stream (from Solid Fuel model to account for enthalpy discrepancies as discussed already).

Figure S5. Block flow diagram of calciner model.

Apart from the input stream connection, the input variables of the model are:

- Pressure drop in the unit, which is considered fixed.

- Heat loss expressed as energy per mass unit of clinker produced, applied in the “Reactor conversion” model.
- Stoichiometry and conversion of reactions in the “Reactor conversion” model. Additionally, the reference compound to which the conversion is referred must be specified.
- False air ingress (FA^{IN}) expressed as the mass of false air per mass unit of clinker produced in the whole process, used to compute the inlet mass flowrate of false air by:

$$\dot{m}_{FA}^{IN} = FA^{IN} \cdot \dot{m}_{clk} \quad (31)$$

- Transport air inlet (TA^{IN}) expressed as the mass of transport air per mass unit of clinker produced in the whole process, used to compute the inlet mass flowrate of transport air by:

$$\dot{m}_{TA}^{IN} = TA^{IN} \cdot \dot{m}_{clk} \quad (32)$$

- Temperature, pressure and molar composition of the false and transport air as provided in Table S3.

2.5 Rotary kiln

In the rotary kiln, additional fuel is burned in the presence of both primary air (cold) and secondary air from the clinker cooler (hot), generating a flame that directly heats the calcined materials from the calciner. The solid temperature gradually rises to 1450°C, completing the calcination of CaCO_3 to CaO and triggering reactions among CaO , SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , and Fe_2O_3 to form clinker phases: belite (C_2S), alite (C_3S), tricalcium aluminate (C_3A), and calcium aluminate ferrite (C_4AF). The high temperatures enhance reaction rates and promote a molten phase, accelerating reactant diffusion. Residual free lime (CaO) remains in the final clinker due to the excess CaO in raw materials and the decomposition of CaSO_4 at high temperatures. Solid particles may be entrained back to the calciner by the combustion gas, moving counter to the main solid flow. False air ingress occurs at both ends of the kiln.

As illustrated in Figure S6, the kiln is modelled in 2 different sections:

- Decomposition (Figure S7): where the residual CaCO_3 decomposes completely into CaO , and phases such as CA , C_2F , and C_2S are largely formed.
- Sintering (Figure S8): where fuel combustion occurs providing the heat to form the the final clinker phases (C_3A , C_4AF and C_3S) and the molten clinker.

Figure S6. Block flow diagram of rotary kiln model.

Both sections in Figure S6 are modelled as a sequence of gPROMS models including “Mixer”, “Reactor conversion” and “Component splitter”.

The Decomposition sub-model includes:

- 3 inlet material streams (solids from the calciner, dusty gas from the sintering section and false air).
- 2 outlet material streams (solids to the Sintering section and exhaust kiln gas to the calciner).

Figure S7. Block flow diagram of the Decomposition section within the rotary kiln model.

Apart from the input stream connection, the input variables of the Decomposition sub-model are:

- Heat loss expressed as energy per mass unit of clinker produced, applied in the “Reactor conversion” model.
- Stoichiometry and conversion of reactions in the “Reactor conversion” model. Additionally, the reference compound to which the conversion is referred must be specified.
- The recirculated dust percentage, which defines the split ratio of solid species entrained by the gas in the “Component splitter” model.
- False air ingress (FA^{IN}) expressed as the mass of false air per mass unit of clinker produced in the whole process, used to compute the inlet mass flowrate of false air by:

$$\dot{m}_{FA}^{IN} = FA^{IN} \cdot \dot{m}_{clk} \quad (2)$$

- Temperature, pressure and molar composition of the false air as provided in Table S3.

Figure S8. Block flow diagram of Sintering section within the rotary kiln model.

The Sintering sub-model includes:

- 5 inlet material streams (solids from the Decomposition section, fuel, secondary air from the clinker cooler, false air and primary air).

- 2 outlet material streams (solids to the clinker cooler and dusty gas to the Decomposition section).
- 1 inlet energy stream (from Solid Fuel model to account for enthalpy discrepancies as discussed already).

As done in the work by Locher (2002), the model considers the additional heat required to form the liquid clinker phase. The calculation is based on the assumptions that the molten clinker consists of C_3A and C_4AF and 10% of C_2S produced in the kiln and that the energy needed for liquid phase formation is 600 kJ/kg of liquid clinker. Apart from the input stream connection, the input variables of the Sintering sub-model are:

- Heat loss expressed as energy per mass unit of clinker produced, applied in the “Reactor conversion” model.
- Stoichiometry and conversion of reactions in the “Reactor conversion” model. Additionally, the reference compound to which the conversion is referred must be specified.
- The recirculated dust percentage, which defines the split ratio of solid species entrained by the gas in the “Component splitter” model.
- False air ingress (FA^{IN}) expressed as the mass of false air per mass unit of clinker produced in the whole process, used to compute the inlet mass flowrate of false air by:

$$\dot{m}_{FA}^{IN} = FA^{IN} \cdot \dot{m}_{clk} \quad (2)$$

- Primary air inlet (PA^{IN}) expressed as the mass of transport air per mass unit of clinker produced in the whole process, used to compute the inlet mass flowrate of transport air by:

$$\dot{m}_{PA}^{IN} = PA^{IN} \cdot \dot{m}_{clk} \quad (2)$$

- Temperature, pressure and molar composition of the false air and primary air as provided in Table S3.

2.6 Clinker cooler

After exiting the kiln, the clinker must be rapidly cooled to around 100°C in the clinker cooler to preserve its microstructure and make it suitable for further processing. The cooler also functions as a heat recovery system, preheating combustion air for the kiln (secondary air) and the calciner (tertiary air). However, some clinker dust may become entrained with the cooling air.

In this study, a grate cooler is assumed and modelled in four sections (Figure S9). Ambient air (see Table S3) is supplied to each of the first three sections to cool the clinker and produce secondary air for the kiln, tertiary air for the calciner, and vent air for the final cooling. The fourth section accounts for heat loss. The model includes:

- 4 inlet material streams (clinker from the kiln and ambient air to each of sections 1 to 3).
- 4 outlet material streams (final clinker product, secondary air to the kiln, tertiary air to the calciner and vent air to the electrostatic precipitator).

Figure S9. Block flow diagram of clinker cooler model.

Sections 1-3 are modelled using a combination of “Heat Exchanger”, “Component Splitter”, and “Mixer” in gPROMS. Due to the crossflow between gas and solids in the grate cooler, the heat exchanger type is set to “Cross flow” and solved using the Logarithmic mean temperature difference (LMTD) method.

Apart from the input stream connection, the input variables for each section are:

- Fixed pressure drop of the gas through the solid bed.
- Heat transfer area (A_{exc}) used as calibration parameter considering typical conditions of cooling air flow. A constant heat transfer coefficient (U_{exc}) between solid and gas of $30 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K})$ is assumed (Bird et al., 2002), simulating the heat exchanger at constant product $A_{exc} \cdot U_{exc}$. This permits to compute the outlet temperatures for air flows other than typical.
- Recirculated dust percentage, which defines the split ratio of solid species entrained by the air flow in the “Component splitter” model.

Section 4 is modelled solely with a "Heat Exchanger" to simulate heat loss from the clinker cooler, expressed as energy per mass of clinker produced.

To calibrate the model and determine A_{exc} for each section, the operating conditions for secondary, tertiary, and vent air indicative of a typical cement plant were used as reference (Table S6).

Table S6. Calibration of exchange area within the clinker cooler model.

Variable		Section 1	Section 2	Section 3
Air flowrate	kg/kg _{clik}	0.43	0.66	1.05
Air temperature outlet	°C	1040	945	275
U_{exc} (set)	W/(m ² ·K)	30	30	30
A_{exc} (computed)	m ²	941	8940	4536

2.7 Modelling assumptions

To simulate the cement reference plant, the following modelling assumptions are made, which apply to the entire study unless otherwise specified.

The properties of raw meal entering the raw mill are summarised in Table S7. It is assumed that the raw meal is fed with an initial moisture content of 7% (mass, wet basis). The composition before drying is calculated to achieve a dry raw meal with a typical composition, as considered by (Campanari et al., 2016) in the framework of the CEMCAP project (CEMCAP, 2015). After drying,

the raw meal temperature reaches 85°C, but due to storage, it is assumed to enter the preheating tower at 60°C. The reference cement plant uses coal as a fuel source. The properties and assumptions for the coal used are based on De Lena et al. (2017) and are shown in Table S8.

Table S7. Properties of raw meal (before and after drying) used as input in the study (Campanari et al., 2016).

Variable		Before drying	After drying
Temperature	°C	20	85
Mass composition			
CaCO ₃	% mass wet	73.76	78.91
SiO ₂	% mass wet	12.84	13.74
Al ₂ O ₃	% mass wet	3.10	3.32
Fe ₂ O ₃	% mass wet	1.87	2.00
MgCO ₃	% mass wet	1.43	1.53
H ₂ O (Moisture)	% mass wet	7.00	0.50

Table S8. Properties of coal (after drying) used as input in the study (De Lena et al., 2017).

Variable		Value
Temperature	°C	60
Higher heating value (HHV)	kJ _{HHV} /kg _{dry coal}	28100
Heat requirements drying	kJ _{th} /kg _{dry coal}	252 ^a
Specific electric consumption milling	kWh _{el} /t _{dry coal}	16.7
Proximate analysis		
H ₂ O (Moisture, M)	% mass wet	1.00
Fixed carbon (FC)	% mass dry	51.26
Volatile matter (VM)	% mass dry	32.16
Ash	% mass dry	16.58
Ultimate analysis		
C	% mass dry	69.35
H	% mass dry	4.02
N	% mass dry	0.50
S	% mass dry	0.50
O	% mass dry	9.05
Ash	% mass dry	16.58
Ash composition		
SiO ₂	% mass ash	43.70
Al ₂ O ₃	% mass ash	32.42
Fe ₂ O ₃	% mass ash	4.00
CaO	% mass ash	18.18
MgO	% mass ash	1.70

^a Estimated assuming to decrease coal moisture content from 8% to 1% (mass, wet basis), with a drying temperature of 80°C

The modelling assumptions for various plant subsections, such as the raw mill, preheating tower, calciner, rotary kiln, and clinker cooler, are presented in Table S9. The reference plant is assumed to require 131.6 kWh/t_{clk} of auxiliary electrical consumption for its operation (IEAGHG, 2013). The electric consumptions of fans, raw mill and coal mill are calculated from the simulation, while all the

other auxiliaries consumption (crushing, solids handling, cement grinding, etc.) are calculated by difference and assumed constant throughout the entire study.

Table S9. Key assumptions for the various units of the reference cement plant.

Variable		Value
Raw mill		
Residual moisture after drying	% mass wet	0.5
False air ingress	% inlet gas mass flowrate	30
Raw mill oversize	% design capacity	15
Specific electric consumption	kWh _{el} /t _{dry meal}	12.5
Preheating tower		From 1st to 5th stage
Pressure drop coefficient	-	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-4} / 8.4 \cdot 10^{-5} / 8.4 \cdot 10^{-5} / 8.4 \cdot 10^{-5} / 6.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Gas velocity cyclone inlet	m/s	12.0 / 11.5 / 12.5 / 14.2 / 15.0
Heat loss ^a	kJ _{th} /kg _{clk}	15 / 15 / 15 / 15 / 0
Cyclone efficiency	%	95 / 86 / 86 / 86 / 76
False air ingress	% inlet gas mass flowrate	1.6 / 1.0 / 1.0 / 1.0 / 0.5
Calcliner		
Pressure drop	bar	0.006
Heat loss	kJ _{th} /kg _{clk}	55
False air ingress	kg _{false air} /kg _{clk}	0.009
Transport air	kg _{transport air} /kg _{clk}	0.022
Rotary kiln		Decomposition / Sintering
Heat loss	kJ _{th} /kg _{clk}	80 / 100
Recirculated dust	%	7 / 3
False air ingress	kg _{false air} /kg _{clk}	0.018 / 0.017
Primary air (only sintering)	kg _{primary air} /kg _{clk}	0.08
Clinker Cooler		From 1st to 3rd section
Pressure drop	bar	0.05 / 0.05 / 0.05
Area exchange (from calibration)	m ²	940 / 9000 / 4600
Recirculated dust ^b	%	2 / 3 / 0
Heat loss (4 th section)	kJ _{th} /kg _{clk}	11.1
Miscellaneous		
Total electric consumption	kWh _{el} /t _{clk}	131.6
Fixed electric consumption (calc.)	kWh _{el} /t _{clk}	98.5
Max. inlet temperature ID fan	°C	530
Max. inlet temperature bag filter	°C	250
Max. inlet temperature ESP	°C	400
Heat loss tertiary air duct	kJ _{th} /kg _{clk}	15
Pressure drop tertiary air duct	bar	0.01
Pressure drop bag filters	bar	0.02
Pressure drop ESP	bar	0.01
ID fans polytropic efficiency	%	85
Filter fans polytropic efficiency	%	83
Cooler fans polytropic efficiency	%	75
Drivers mechanical efficiency	%	95

^a Heat loss of the 5th preheating stage is merged with the heat loss of the calciner.

^b Recirculated dust in the 3rd cooler section is not considered since the entrained clinker dust is then recovered in an electrostatic precipitator and mixed back with the produced clinker, not affecting the overall material balance.

The chemical reactions simulated in different stages of the reference cement plant, along with their respective conversion rates and reference compounds are detailed in Table S10. These reactions are assumed to occur in series, with the order of reactions being critical for the modelling.

Table S10. Reactions set in different units of the reference plant with conversion rates assumed and reference compound.

Reaction	Reference compound	Conversion (%)
4th preheating stage		
$\text{MgCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{MgO} + \text{CO}_2$	MgCO_3	100
$\text{CaO} + \text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{CaCO}_3$	CaO	35
Calcliner		
$\text{S} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{SO}_2$	S	100
$2\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	H_2	100
$2\text{C} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{CO}$	C	98
$2\text{CO} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{CO}_2$	CO	98
$\text{CaCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{CaO} + \text{CO}_2$	CaCO_3	92
$\text{MgCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{MgO} + \text{CO}_2$	MgCO_3	100
$\text{CaO} + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow \text{CA}$	Al_2O_3	27
$2\text{CaO} + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{F}$	Fe_2O_3	27
$2\text{CaO} + \text{SiO}_2 \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{S}$	SiO_2	24.2
$2\text{CaO} + \text{O}_2 + 2\text{SO}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{CaSO}_4$	SO_2	100
Kiln (Decomposition)		
$\text{S} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{SO}_2$	S	100
$2\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	H_2	100
$2\text{C} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{CO}$	C	100
$2\text{CO} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{CO}_2$	CO	100
$\text{CaCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{CaO} + \text{CO}_2$	CaCO_3	100
$\text{MgCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{MgO} + \text{CO}_2$	MgCO_3	100
$\text{CaO} + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow \text{CA}$	Al_2O_3	100
$2\text{CaO} + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{F}$	Fe_2O_3	100
$2\text{CaO} + \text{SiO}_2 \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{S}$	SiO_2	95.1
$\text{CaSO}_4 + \text{C} \rightarrow \text{CaO} + \text{CO} + \text{SO}_2$	C	10.6
$2\text{CaSO}_4 \rightarrow 2\text{CaO} + \text{O}_2 + 2\text{SO}_2$	CaSO_4	10.6
Kiln (Sintering)		
$\text{S} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{SO}_2$	S	100
$2\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	H_2	100
$2\text{C} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{CO}$	C	100
$2\text{CO} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{CO}_2$	CO	100
$\text{CaCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{CaO} + \text{CO}_2$	CaCO_3	100
$\text{MgCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{MgO} + \text{CO}_2$	MgCO_3	100
$\text{CaO} + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow \text{CA}$	Al_2O_3	100
$2\text{CaO} + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{F}$	Fe_2O_3	100
$2\text{CaO} + \text{SiO}_2 \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{S}$	SiO_2	100
$\text{CaO} + \text{CA} + \text{C}_2\text{F} \rightarrow \text{C}_4\text{AF}$	C_2F	100
$2\text{CaO} + \text{CA} \rightarrow \text{C}_3\text{A}$	CA	100
$\text{CaSO}_4 + \text{C} \rightarrow \text{CaO} + \text{CO} + \text{SO}_2$	C	92.8
$2\text{CaSO}_4 \rightarrow 2\text{CaO} + \text{O}_2 + 2\text{SO}_2$	CaSO_4	92.8
$\text{CaO} + \text{C}_2\text{S} \rightarrow \text{C}_3\text{S}$	C_2S	74.5

The conversions listed in Table S10 are designed to approximate the composition evolution of minerals at various stages of the clinker production process, as detailed in Hewlett and Liska (2019). The recarbonation reaction between CaO and CO₂ may take place where temperature and CO₂ partial pressure are favourable, forming CaCO₃ and developing heat (Bhatty et al., 2011). Unlike most studies available in the literature, this work includes the effect of this reaction, which is assumed to take place in the last preheating stage before the calciner. The conversion of this reaction is assumed to be 70% of the conversion predicted by thermodynamic equilibrium, to account for kinetic limitations. MgCO₃ calcination takes place at lower temperatures than CaCO₃ calcination, with complete decomposition at temperatures above 700-750°C (Bhatty et al., 2011). For this reason, 100% conversion is assumed for the MgCO₃ → MgO + CO₂ reaction from the last preheating cyclone onwards.

The combustion reactions for S and H₂ are included for modelling purposes, but these reactions do not occur as modelled, in reality. Instead, they are considered to account for the heat released during the combustion of the sulphur and hydrogen content in the coal. The combustion of C to CO₂ proceeds in two steps, producing CO as an intermediate. This approach allows the model to account for incomplete burnout. In the calciner, the conversion for both steps of the carbon combustion process is set at 98%, reflecting incomplete burnout and partial combustion. As a result, the model predicts the emission of CO from the process. On the contrary, complete combustion of coal is assumed in the rotary kiln.

In order to meet the target clinker production rate and ensure correct operation, several design variables are set to a target value. Table S11 provides a summary of the key design specifications and the corresponding manipulated variables.

Table S11. Design specifications set for the correct operation of the reference plant and associated manipulated variables.

Design specification		Value	Manipulated variable
Clinker production	kg/s	35	Raw meal flowrate
Drying temperature raw mill	°C	85	Split ratio exhaust gas to raw mill
Outlet temperature calciner	°C	870	Fuel flowrate to calciner
Outlet O ₂ concentration calciner	% mol wet	2.5	Tertiary air flowrate
Clinker outlet temperature kiln	°C	1450	Fuel flowrate to kiln
Outlet O ₂ concentration kiln	% mol wet	5.0	Secondary air flowrate
Clinker outlet temperature cooler	°C	95	Vent air flowrate

2.8 Validation

To ensure the accuracy of the developed model, it was compared against the model established by the CEMCAP project and reported in the project deliverable D4.1 (Campanari et al., 2016). The key outcomes of this comparison, as shown in the following, demonstrate a high degree of similarity between the results, validating the reliability of the model proposed by this study.

of secondary and tertiary air flows remains similar in both cases (1.09 kg/kg_{clik} in this work compared to 1.13 kg/kg_{clik} in Campanari et al., 2016).

Another difference is the reduction in the amount of coal required to meet the process heat demand, which is 1.8% lower in this study. This is primarily linked to the reduced raw meal input necessary to achieve the same clinker output. As a result, the model developed by this study predicts a lower overall CO₂ emission compared to the model proposed in the CEMCAP framework.

Table S12. Overall performance of the reference cement plant modelled in this study and within the CEMCAP framework (Campanari et al., 2016).

Variable		Developed model	CEMCAP model	Relative error
Clinker production	kg/s	32.7	32.7	0.0%
Total fuel input	kg/s	3.80	3.87	1.8%
Raw meal feed	kg/kg _{clik}	1.63	1.66	2.2%
Fuel to calciner/kiln	%	60.6/39.4	62.0/38.8	2.3%
Secondary air	kg/kg _{clik}	0.428	0.330	29.4%
Tertiary air	kg/kg _{clik}	0.662	0.801	17.3%
Heat input	GJ _{LHV} /t _{clik}	3.128	3.197	2.2%
CO ₂ emissions	kg _{CO2} /t _{clik}	833	863	3.5%

Table S13 compares the final clinker composition (stream #8 of Figure S10), showing general agreement between the two models. The model proposed predicts a slightly lower amount of C₃S: 63.1% compared to 64.5% in Campanari et al., (2016). This lower conversion of C₂S and CaO into C₃S was intentionally adjusted to obtain a higher content of free lime in the final clinker. This adjustment aligns the model more closely with real-world conditions, where free lime content typically ranges between 1% and 1.5%, as reported by Hewlett and Liska (2019).

Table S13. Final clinker composition predicted by this study and by CEMCAP model (Campanari et al., 2016).

Species		Developed model	CEMCAP model
CaO	% mass dry	1.1	0.8
MgO	% mass dry	1.2	1.1
C ₂ S	% mass dry	15.0	14
C ₃ S	% mass dry	63.1	64.5
C ₃ A	% mass dry	9.8	9.8
C ₄ AF	% mass dry	9.6	9.6

Table S14 compares the flue gas composition exiting the preheating tower and directed to the raw mill for drying (stream #20). Additionally, to validate the accuracy of the raw mill model, the flue gas composition at the stack (stream #24), is compared to the results from the CEMCAP project as reported by Voldsund et al. (2019) under “Low air leak in mill” conditions (30% of drying gas flow, consistent with this work). As illustrated in Table S14, the predicted composition is well-aligned, with only a minor discrepancy in the gas temperature.

Table S14. Gas molar composition at the preheating tower outlet and stack, as predicted by this study and by CEMCAP model (Campanari et al., 2016; Voldsund et al., 2019).

Variable	Outlet preheating tower (stream #20)		Stack (stream #24)	
	Developed model	CEMCAP model	Developed model	CEMCAP model
Temperature °C	319.5	314.4	112.1	130
CO ₂ % mol wet	31.2	31.9	22.2	22
O ₂ % mol wet	3.5	3.3	6.9	7
N ₂ % mol wet	59.0	59.0	58.1	60
H ₂ O % mol wet	5.4	5.1	12.1	11
Ar % mol wet	0.7	0.7	0.7	0

For completeness, key variables of the streams shown in Figure 10 are summarised in Table S15. For raw meal streams entering the preheating tower, any solid composition not summing to 100% represents the moisture content.

Table S15. Stream table of the reference cement plant detailed in Figure S10.

Stream	T	P	Phase	Mass flow kg/s	Gas composition (% mol wet)							Solid composition (% mass wet)																
					O ₂	N ₂	CO	CO ₂	H ₂ O	Ar	SO ₂	CaCO ₃	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgCO ₃	CaO	MgO	C ₂ S	C ₃ S	C ₃ A	C ₄ AF	CA	C ₂ F	CaSO ₄			
1	85.0	-	Solid	56.50	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	78.9	13.7	3.3	2.0	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0			
2	60.0	-	Solid	56.93	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	78.9	13.7	3.3	2.0	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0			
3	319.5	-	Solid	63.68	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	79.3	13.8	3.3	2.0	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0			
4	507.7	-	Solid	63.76	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	79.0	13.8	3.3	2.0	1.5	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0			
5	665.3	-	Solid	64.27	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	77.7	13.7	3.3	2.0	1.3	0.9	0.1	0.7	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1			
6	802.3	-	Solid	67.39	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	69.7	13.4	3.2	1.9	0.0	5.0	0.8	3.8	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.6	0.3	0.7			
7	867.8	-	Solid	40.73	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7.0	13.1	3.2	1.8	0.0	42.7	1.1	20.0	1.9	0.3	0.3	2.9	1.8	3.8			
8	95.0	-	Solid	35.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1	1.2	15.0	63.1	9.8	9.6	0.0	0.0	0.2			
9	60.0	-	Coal	2.46	See Table S8																							
10	60.0	-	Coal	1.60	See Table S8																							
11	1040.7	1.000	Gas	14.97	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
			Solid	0.74	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1	1.2	15.0	63.1	9.8	9.6	0.0	0.0	0.2		
12	1119.1	1.000	Gas	22.42	5.0	70.4	0.0	16.9	5.4	0.8	1.4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
			Solid	2.83	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	20.8	1.1	56.4	3.7	0.6	0.6	7.9	4.9	3.4		
13	925.7	0.990	Gas	23.20	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
			Solid	1.08	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1	1.2	15.0	63.1	9.8	9.6	0.0	0.0	0.2		
14	276.7	1.000	Gas	36.41	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-			
15	870.0	0.984	Gas	66.88	2.5	57.6	0.1	34.3	4.8	0.7	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
			Solid	53.60	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7.0	13.1	3.2	1.8	0.0	42.7	1.1	20.0	1.9	0.3	0.3	2.9	1.8	3.8		
16	867.8	0.979	Gas	67.21	2.6	57.7	0.1	34.1	4.8	0.7	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
			Solid	12.86	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7.0	13.1	3.2	1.8	0.0	42.7	1.1	20.0	1.9	0.3	0.3	2.9	1.8	3.8		
17	802.3	0.973	Gas	66.65	2.8	58.7	0.1	32.8	4.8	0.7	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
			Solid	10.97	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	69.7	13.4	3.2	1.9	0.0	5.0	0.8	3.8	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.6	0.3	0.7		
18	665.3	0.967	Gas	67.32	3.1	58.9	0.1	32.4	4.8	0.7	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
			Solid	10.46	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	77.7	13.7	3.3	2.0	1.3	0.9	0.1	0.7	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1		
19	507.7	0.961	Gas	67.99	3.3	59.1	0.1	32.0	4.8	0.7	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
			Solid	10.38	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	79.0	13.8	3.3	2.0	1.5	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0		

3. CO₂ quality specifications and CPU modelling

The quality specifications of the captured CO₂ depend on the transportation method and the final destination, whether for storage or utilisation in a production process. Magli et al. (2022) reviewed these specifications, defining two limiting conditions. Here we adopt the “Moderate Purity” specifications (Magli et al., 2022) as detailed in Table S16.

Table S16. CO₂ quality specifications assumed for transport and storage (Magli et al., 2022).

Variable		Value
Pressure	bar	110
Temperature	°C	30
Total non condensables	mol	< 4
CO ₂	mol	> 95
H ₂ O	ppm	< 1
O ₂	ppm	< 4
N ₂	mol	< 2
Ar	mol	< 4
CH ₄	mol	< 4
H ₂	mol	< 0.75
CO	mol	< 0.2

The CO₂ compression and purification unit (CPU) is the stage where the CO₂ is conditioned, purified and compressed to meet the quality specifications for transport and storage. In the low-carbon scenarios presented in this study, the CO₂ stream entering the CPU already satisfies the purity specifications outlined in Table 4, except for the H₂O content. Consequently, the CPU is responsible for the final compression and dehydration of the CO₂. The CPU proposed is based on those suggested by Anantharaman et al. (2017) and Magli et al. (2022) and is illustrated in Figure S11.

Figure S11. Process flow diagram of the CPU.

The CO₂ is compressed in a four-stage compressor up to 80 bar (stream #5 in Figure S11) with a constant pressure ratio and intercooling to 28°C. The intercoolers (INTERC) are assumed to be plate and frame heat exchangers (Gardarsdottir et al., 2019) operated with refrigerated water (15–25°C). Knock-out drums for water condensation are placed after each of the first two stages. A dehydration step (DEHYD), using solid bed adsorption with thermal regeneration, is employed after the second compression stage (stream # 2) for complete water removal. A small fraction (10%) of the

dehydrated CO₂ is recycled for bed regeneration (stream #3). After compression to 80 bar, the CO₂ is liquefied at 20°C (stream #6) and pumped to 110 bar, ready for transportation (stream #7). Detailed assumptions for CPU modelling are provided in Table S17.

Table S17. Key assumptions for the CO₂ compression and purification unit (Magli et al., 2022).

Variable		Value
Outlet pressure multistage compressor	bar	80
Outlet pressure CO ₂ pump	bar	110
Pressure drop compressor intercoolers (gas side)	bar	0.3
Pressure drop dehydration unit (gas side)	bar	1.00
Electrical consumption dehydration unit	kW _e /kg _{H₂O}	2.29
CO ₂ pump isentropic efficiency	%	83
Compressor polytropic efficiency	%	87

4. Low-carbon configurations modelling

This study investigates low-carbon cement plants that combine calciner electrification and amine-based capture, differing in the calciner technology – entrainment (Ent) vs. drop tube (DT) – and in the heat recovery strategy for the hot CO₂ exiting the electrified calciner. The heat content of the CO₂-rich stream can either be used to preheat the raw materials (RMP configuration) or transferred to a fraction of the vent air from the clinker cooler via a gas-gas heat exchanger (GGHX configuration), with the hot vent air then preheating the raw materials. For the post-combustion capture (PCC) stage, monoethanolamine (MEA) was selected as the solvent due to the technology maturity (Schneider et al., 2023) and the availability of significant waste heat for MEA regeneration in low-carbon processes. The two methods of handling the CO₂ stream, combined with the two calciner types, yield four design alternatives: DT-RMP, Ent-RMP, DT-GGHX, and Ent-GGHX depicted in Figures from S12 to S15, respectively.

The modelling of these low-carbon configurations follows the approach established for the reference plant, with key assumptions tailored to each heat recovery strategy. Detailed assumptions are provided in Table S18 for RMP configurations and Table S19 for GGHX configurations, overriding those in Section 2.7. Where not specified, assumptions from the reference plant apply.

The low-carbon configurations aim to minimise design impacts on the cement manufacturing process. The secondary air flowrate in the rotary kiln is set at the same value as in the reference case. Similarly, tertiary air flow is controlled to achieve a temperature of 400°C entering the third section of the clinker cooler.

For RMP configurations, a new preheating tower is added. This modification reduces cyclone sizing compared to the reference plant, as the two separate strings handle lower gas flowrates. Consequently, heat losses in each cyclone are also reduced and distributed between the two strings. In the DT-RMP design, the gas flowrate in the kiln string is double that in the calciner string, leading to corresponding heat losses of 10 kJ_{th}/kg_{clik} in the kiln string and 5 kJ_{th}/kg_{clik} in the calciner string, compared to a total of 15 kJ_{th}/kg_{clik} in the reference plant. Conversely, in the Ent-RMP design, CO₂ recycling results in a

larger gas flowrate in the calciner string almost double that of the kiln string. Accordingly, heat losses are set to 5 kJ_{th}/kg_{clk} in the kiln string and 10 kJ_{th}/kg_{clk} in the calciner string.

The distribution of raw meal between the two preheating strings is adjusted to achieve outlet temperatures of 400°C at the top of DT-RMP calciner string and 530°C at the top of Ent-RMP calciner string. Furthermore, it is assumed that false air ingress in the cyclones can be reduced by 80% compared to the reference plant through improved construction and maintenance, thereby minimising CO₂ dilution. A share of the tertiary air is used to control the kiln string bottom temperature at 765°C, avoiding undesired calcination in the preheaters.

Table S18. Key assumptions for configurations with pure CO₂ stream preheating raw meal.

Variable		DT-RMP	Ent-RMP
Preheating tower (calciner string)		From 1st to 3rd stage	
Cyclone efficiency	%	95/86/86	95/86/86
Heat loss ^a	kJ _{th} /kg _{clk}	5/5/5	10/10/10
False air ingress	% inlet gas mass flowrate	0.32/0.20/0.20	0.32/0.20/0.20
Conversion in 3 rd stage for CaO + CO ₂ → CaCO ₃	%	100 ^a	21
Preheating tower (kiln string)		From 1st to 3rd stage	
Cyclone efficiency kiln string	%	95/86/86	95/86/86
Heat loss ^a	kJ _{th} /kg _{clk}	10/10/10	5/5/5
False air ingress	% inlet gas mass flowrate	0.32/0.20/0.20	0.32/0.20/0.20
Calciner			
Temperature	°C	920	920
Solid entrainment	%	5	-
Calciner cyclone efficiency	%	-	84
Specifications		Logic	
Secondary air		Same flowrate as in Ref. Plant (14.97 kg/s)	Same flowrate as in Ref. Plant (14.97 kg/s)
Tertiary air		Clinker temperature entering 3 rd cooler section as in Ref. Plant (400°C)	Clinker temperature entering 3 rd cooler section as in Ref. Plant (400°C)
Raw meal split		400°C at top of calciner string	530°C at top of calciner string
Tertiary air to kiln string		Solid temperature of 765°C from bottom stage kiln string	Solid temperature of 765°C from bottom stage kiln string
CO ₂ recycle to calciner		-	Gas volumetric flowrate entering calciner is 50% of that in Ref. Plant

^a Temperature and CO₂ partial pressure are such that the thermodynamic equilibrium predicts complete consumption of CaO

For GGHX configurations, the heat content of the CO₂-rich stream is transferred to a portion of vent air from the clinker cooler via a gas-gas heat exchanger. The rerouted vent air fraction matches the gas mass flow entering the reference plant preheating tower, while its outlet temperature is regulated to maintain a maximum temperature of 765°C at the bottom of the kiln string, as previously described.

In both configurations, the calciner temperature is raised to 920°C to account for increased CO₂ partial pressure while maintaining a calcination rate of 92%. For Ent-calciners, the CO₂ recycle rate ensures 50% of the volumetric flowrate at the calciner entrance of the reference plant to provide a certain gas flow to lift the solids.

Table S19. Key assumptions for configurations with pure CO₂ stream preheating vent air via a gas-gas heat exchanger.

Variable		DT-GGHX	Ent-GGHX
Calciner			
Temperature	°C	920	920
Solid entrainment	%	5	-
Calciner cyclone efficiency	%	-	84
Specifications		Logic	
Secondary air		Same flowrate as in Ref. Plant (14.97 kg/s)	Same flowrate as in Ref. Plant (14.97 kg/s)
Tertiary air		Clinker temperature entering 3 rd cooler section as in Ref. Plant (400°C)	Clinker temperature entering 3 rd cooler section as in Ref. Plant (400°C)
Logic for vent air split		Same gas flowrate to Reference Plant as in base case (67.2 kg/s)	Same gas flowrate to Reference Plant as in base case (67.2 kg/s)
Logic vent air temperature in gas-gas heat exchanger outlet		Solid temperature of 765°C from bottom stage kiln string	Solid temperature of 765°C from bottom stage kiln string
Logic for CO ₂ recycling to calciner		-	Gas volumetric flowrate entering calciner is 50% of that in Ref. Plant

Unlike Ent-calciners, DT-calciners do not require a calciner cyclone, as the solids descend within the unit, while the CO₂ released is collected at the top. However, 5% of solids are assumed to remain entrained with the CO₂ gas flow. Conversely, Ent-calciners require a calciner cyclone as the solids are fully entrained in the gas flow. Due to the reduced gas flowrate compared to the reference plant, the solid load exiting the calciner is higher. Thus, the cyclone efficiency is increased to 84% to maintain a constant solid-to-gas ratio of approximately 70 g/m³, as in the reference plant.

Additional assumptions related to auxiliary units are summarised in Table S20.

Table S20. Additional assumptions for auxiliary units of low-carbon processes.

Variable		Value
U_{exc} for low pressure gas – low pressure gas	W/(m ² ·K)	30
U_{exc} for low pressure gas - water	W/(m ² ·K)	60
U_{exc} for high pressure gas - water	W/(m ² ·K)	350
Pressure drop GGHX (CO ₂ side)	bar	0.043
Pressure drop GGHX (Vent air side)	bar	0.036
Pressure drop evaporator (gas side)	bar	0.01
Pressure drop cooler (gas side)	bar	0.01
CO ₂ recycle fan polytropic efficiency	%	85

The pressure drop across the gas-gas heat exchanger (GGHX in Figures S13 and S15), is based on data from Jacob and Tokheim (2023), who conducted a dedicated study on this unit. Heat transfer coefficients (U_{exc}) are assigned according to the fluid types involved in each heat exchanger. For the Air Heater (Figure S12) and GGHX units, which involve heat transfer between low-pressure gases, a U_{exc} of 30 W/(m²·K) is used (Towler and Sinnott, 2021). For evaporators (labelled WHR in Figures from S12 to S15) and coolers, where heat transfer occurs between water and low-pressure gas, U_{exc} is set to 60 W/(m²·K) (Green and Southard, 2018). Finally, for intercoolers between compression stages, where compressed gas exchanges heat with water, U_{exc} is set to 350 W/(m²·K) (Green and Southard, 2018).

To effectively operate the MEA capture process and the selective non-catalytic reduction (SNCR) unit, the make-up of certain utilities and a certain cooling duty are required, as presented in Table S21.

Table S21. Utilities make-up and cooling duty requirements for MEA capture process and selective non-catalytic reduction unit.

Variable		Value	Reference
Cooling duty MEA	MJ _{th} /kg _{CO2} captured in MEA process	3.00	Gardarsdottir et al., 2019
MEA make-up	kg/kg _{CO2} captured in MEA process	0.0015	Manzolini et al., 2015
NaOH make-up	kg/kg _{CO2} captured in MEA process	0.001	Voldsund et al., 2019
Process water make-up	kg/kg _{CO2} captured in MEA process	0.5	Voldsund et al., 2019
NH ₃ make-up	kg/kg _{CO2} emitted by fuel combustion	0.006	Gardarsdottir et al., 2019

Details of the main streams for each configuration (DT-RMP, Ent-RMP, DT-GGHX, and Ent-GGHX) are provided in Tables from S22 to S25, respectively.

Figure S12. DT-RMP configuration scheme: drop tube calciner with pure CO₂ preheating raw meal.

Table S22. Stream table of the drop tube calciner with pure CO₂ preheating raw meal configuration detailed in Figure S12.

Stream	T	P	Phase	Mass flow	Gas composition (% mol wet)							Solid composition (% mol wet)														
					O ₂	N ₂	CO	CO ₂	H ₂ O	Ar	SO ₂	CaCO ₃	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgCO ₃	CaO	MgO	C ₂ S	C ₃ S	C ₃ A	C ₄ AF	CA	C ₂ F	CaSO ₄	
1	85.1	-	Solid	54.16	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	78.4	14.0	3.5	2.0	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
2	60.0	-	Solid	57.54	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	78.5	14.0	3.5	2.0	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
3	60.0	-	Solid	15.17	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	78.5	14.0	3.5	2.0	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
4	60.0	-	Solid	42.38	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	78.5	14.0	3.5	2.0	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
5	848.7	-	Solid	16.94	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	77.4	13.5	3.4	1.9	0.0	0.0	0.8	2.2	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.2	0.0	
6	765.0	-	Solid	42.87	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	73.0	13.1	3.3	1.9	0.0	1.5	0.8	4.0	1.3	0.2	0.2	0.5	0.3	0.0	
7	919.7	-	Solid	39.76	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8.5	14.3	3.5	2.0	0.0	46.5	1.1	18.1	1.4	0.2	0.2	2.6	1.7	0.0	
8	97.7	-	Solid	35.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	1.2	15.2	63.2	9.7	9.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	
9	60.0	-	Coal	2.46	See Table S8																					
10	1039.3	1.000	Gas	14.97	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
			Solid	0.73	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	1.2	15.2	63.2	9.7	9.6	0.0	0.0	0.0
11	1145.3	1.000	Gas	21.63	6.7	71.7	0.0	15.9	4.9	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
			Solid	2.76	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	22.8	1.1	58.0	3.2	0.5	0.5	8.1	5.1	0.0
12	923.7	0.990	Gas	22.86	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
			Solid	1.07	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	1.2	15.2	63.2	9.7	9.6	0.0	0.0	0.0
13	923.7	0.990	Gas	15.77	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
			Solid	0.74	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	1.2	15.2	63.2	9.7	9.6	0.0	0.0	0.0
14	923.7	0.990	Gas	7.09	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
			Solid	0.33	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	1.2	15.2	63.2	9.7	9.6	0.0	0.0	0.0
15	271.6	1.000	Gas	35.83	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
16	250.0	1.000	Gas	16.00	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
17	352.2	0.990	Gas	58.92	0.0	29.7	30.3	2.0	2.0	0.0	2.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
			Solid	0.33	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	12.3	0.1	12.4	0.0	11.1	1.3	11.8	0.6	11.8	0.6	11.8	0.6	12.4	12.4
18	350.0	1.000	Gas	58.92	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0															
19	919.7	0.994	Gas	17.98	0.0	0.1	0.0	99.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
			Solid	2.09	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8.5	14.3	3.5	2.0	0.0	46.5	1.1	18.1	1.4	0.2	0.2	2.6	1.7	0.0
20	400.0	0.967	Gas	17.53	0.3	1.0	0.0	97.8	1.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
			Solid	0.89	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	78.8	14.0	3.5	2.0	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

Figure S13. Ent-RMP configuration scheme: entrainment calciner with pure CO₂ preheating raw meal.

Table S23. Stream table of the entrainment calciner with pure CO₂ preheating raw meal configuration detailed in Figure S13.

Stream	T	P	Phase	Mass flow kg/s	Gas composition (% mol wet)							Solid composition (% mol wet)													
					O ₂	N ₂	CO	CO ₂	H ₂ O	Ar	SO ₂	CaCO ₃	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgCO ₃	CaO	MgO	C ₂ S	C ₃ S	C ₃ A	C ₄ AF	CA	C ₂ F	CaSO ₄
1	85.0	-	Solid	54.17	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	78.4	14.0	3.5	2.0	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
2	60.0	-	Solid	56.71	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	78.5	14.0	3.5	2.0	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
3	60.0	-	Solid	23.34	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	78.5	14.0	3.5	2.0	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
4	60.0	-	Solid	33.37	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	78.5	14.0	3.5	2.0	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
5	878.9	-	Solid	29.75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	64.8	13.8	3.4	2.0	0.0	8.9	0.8	4.9	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.5	0.0
6	765.0	-	Solid	33.91	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	72.7	13.0	3.3	1.9	0.0	1.9	0.8	4.8	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.7	0.4	0.0
7	919.6	-	Solid	39.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7.7	14.1	3.4	1.9	0.0	46.9	1.1	19.5	0.5	0.1	0.1	2.9	1.8	0.0
8	103.2	-	Solid	35.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	1.2	15.4	62.9	9.7	9.6	0.0	0.0	0.0
9	60.0	-	Coal	2.46	See Table S8																				
10	1037.1	1.000	Gas	14.97	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
			Solid	0.72	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	1.2	15.4	62.9	9.7	9.6	0.0	0.0
11	1151.3	1.000	Gas	21.45	7.0	72.1	0.0	15.3	4.8	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
			Solid	2.72	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	23.1	1.1	58.7	2.3	0.4	0.3	8.2	5.1
12	920.9	0.990	Gas	22.37	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
			Solid	1.06	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	1.2	15.4	62.9	9.7	9.6	0.0	0.0
13	920.9	0.990	Gas	4.16	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
			Solid	0.20	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	1.2	15.4	62.9	9.7	9.6	0.0	0.0
14	920.9	0.990	Gas	18.21	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
			Solid	0.86	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	1.2	15.4	62.9	9.7	9.6	0.0	0.0
15	273.8	1.000	Gas	34.93	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
16	400.0	0.980	Gas	53.13	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
			Solid	0.86	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	1.2	15.4	62.9	9.7	9.6	0.0	0.0
17	399.8	1.000	Gas	53.13	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
18	399.8	1.000	Gas	48.68	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
19	399.8	1.000	Gas	4.46	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
20	920.0	0.994	Gas	42.38	0.3	1.3	0.0	97.5	0.9	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
			Solid	46.44	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7.7	14.1	3.4	1.9	0.0	46.9	1.1	19.5	0.5	0.1	0.1	2.9	1.8

Figure S14. DT-GGHX configuration scheme: drop tube calciner with pure CO₂ preheating vent air via a gas-gas heat exchanger.

Table S24. Stream table of the drop tube calciner with pure CO₂ preheating vent air via a gas-gas heat exchanger configuration detailed in Figure S14.

Stream	T	P	Phase	Mass flow	Gas composition (% mol wet)							Solid composition (% mol wet)															
					O ₂	N ₂	CO	CO ₂	H ₂ O	Ar	SO ₂	CaCO ₃	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgCO ₃	CaO	MgO	C ₂ S	C ₃ S	C ₃ A	C ₄ AF	CA	C ₂ F	CaSO ₄		
1	85.0	-	Solid	56.77	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	78.4	14.0	3.5	2.0	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0		
2	60.0	-	Solid	57.55	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	78.4	14.0	3.5	2.0	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0		
3	765.0	-	Solid	57.31	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	74.1	13.2	3.3	1.9	0.0	1.1	0.8	3.1	1.4	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.0		
4	918.7	-	Solid	38.12	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8.5	14.3	3.5	2.0	0.0	46.4	1.1	17.5	2.0	0.3	0.3	2.5	1.6	0.0		
5	250.0	-	Solid	2.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8.5	14.3	3.5	2.0	0.0	46.4	1.1	17.5	2.0	0.3	0.3	2.5	1.6	0.0		
6	887.0	-	Solid	40.13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8.5	14.3	3.5	2.0	0.0	46.4	1.1	17.5	2.0	0.3	0.3	2.5	1.6	0.0		
7	95.0	-	Solid	35.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.2	1.2	15.1	63.3	9.7	9.6	0.0	0.0	0.0		
8	60.0	-	Coal	1.41	See Table S8																						
9	1040.6	1.000	Gas	14.97	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
			Solid	0.74	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.2	1.2	15.1	63.3	9.7	9.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	
10	1126.2	1.000	Gas	21.67	6.4	71.6	0.0	16.2	5.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
			Solid	2.78	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	22.6	1.1	57.6	3.8	0.6	0.6	8.0	5.0	0.0	
11	925.4	0.990	Gas	23.18	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
			Solid	1.08	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.2	1.2	15.1	63.3	9.7	9.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	
12	274.8	1.000	Gas	36.41	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
13	280.3	1.036	Gas	36.41	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
14	280.3	1.036	Gas	22.38	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
15	280.3	1.036	Gas	14.02	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
16	160.0	1.026	Gas	14.02	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
17	654.8	1.000	Gas	22.38	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
18	914.4	0.990	Gas	67.23	16.3	75.5	0.0	5.0	2.2	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
			Solid	3.87	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	16.6	1.1	45.7	20.5	3.1	3.1	5.8	3.6	0.0	
19	920.0	0.994	Gas	17.27	0.2	0.6	0.0	99.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
			Solid	2.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8.5	14.3	3.5	2.0	0.0	46.4	1.1	17.5	2.0	0.3	0.3	2.5	1.6	0.0	
20	526.0	0.951	Gas	17.27	0.2	0.6	0.0	99.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
			Solid	2.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8.5	14.3	3.5	2.0	0.0	46.4	1.1	17.5	2.0	0.3	0.3	2.5	1.6	0.0	
21	250.0	0.941	Gas	17.27	0.2	0.6	0.0	99.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
			Solid	2.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8.5	14.3	3.5	2.0	0.0	46.4	1.1	17.5	2.0	0.3	0.3	2.5	1.6	0.0	

Table S25. Stream table of the entrainment calciner with pure CO₂ preheating vent air via a gas-gas heat exchanger configuration detailed in Figure S15.

Stream	T	P	Phase	Mass flow kg/s	Gas composition (% mol wet)							Solid composition (% mol wet)															
					O ₂	N ₂	CO	CO ₂	H ₂ O	Ar	SO ₂	CaCO ₃	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgCO ₃	CaO	MgO	C ₂ S	C ₃ S	C ₃ A	C ₄ AF	CA	C ₂ F	CaSO ₄		
1	85.0	-	Solid	56.77	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	78.4	14.0	3.5	2.0	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0		
2	60.0	-	Solid	57.55	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	78.4	14.0	3.5	2.0	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0		
3	765.0	-	Solid	57.31	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	74.1	13.2	3.3	1.9	0.0	1.1	0.8	3.1	1.4	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.0		
4	918.0	-	Solid	37.11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7.8	14.0	3.4	1.9	0.0	46.2	1.1	18.6	2.0	0.3	0.3	2.7	1.7	0.0		
5	250.0	-	Solid	2.89	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7.8	14.0	3.4	1.9	0.0	46.2	1.1	18.6	2.0	0.3	0.3	2.7	1.7	0.0		
6	872.1	-	Solid	40.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7.8	14.0	3.4	1.9	0.0	46.2	1.1	18.6	2.0	0.3	0.3	2.7	1.7	0.0		
7	95.0	-	Solid	35.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.2	1.2	15.1	63.3	9.7	9.6	0.0	0.0	0.0		
8	60.0	-	Coal	1.42	See Table S8																						
9	1040.6	1.000	Gas	14.97	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
			Solid	0.74	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.2	1.2	15.1	63.3	9.7	9.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	
10	1120.7	1.000	Gas	21.55	6.3	71.9	0.0	15.9	5.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
			Solid	2.78	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	22.6	1.1	57.6	3.8	0.6	0.6	8.0	5.0	0.0	
11	925.4	0.990	Gas	23.18	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
			Solid	1.08	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.2	1.2	15.1	63.3	9.7	9.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	
12	274.8	1.000	Gas	36.41	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
13	280.3	1.036	Gas	36.41	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
14	280.3	1.036	Gas	22.51	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
15	280.3	1.036	Gas	13.90	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
16	160.0	1.260	Gas	13.90	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
17	664.2	1.000	Gas	22.51	20.7	77.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
18	914.4	0.990	Gas	67.23	16.3	75.6	0.0	4.9	2.2	0.9	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
			Solid	3.87	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	16.6	1.1	45.7	20.5	3.1	3.1	5.8	3.6	0.0	
19	920.0	0.994	Gas	42.64	0.2	0.8	0.0	98.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
			Solid	44.17	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7.8	14.0	3.4	1.9	0.0	46.2	1.1	18.6	2.0	0.3	0.3	2.7	1.7	0.0	
20	918.0	0.987	Gas	42.86	0.4	1.4	0.0	98.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
			Solid	7.07	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7.8	14.0	3.4	1.9	0.0	46.2	1.1	18.6	2.0	0.3	0.3	2.7	1.7	0.0	
21	764.7	0.944	Gas	42.86	0.4	1.4	0.0	98.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
			Solid	7.07	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7.8	14.0	3.4	1.9	0.0	46.2	1.1	18.6	2.0	0.3	0.3	2.7	1.7	0.0	

5. Cost correlations and parameters for economic analysis

The cost correlations for estimating the equipment cost (EC) of various process units are detailed in Table S26, which also includes the associated scaling parameters and installation factors (IF) to compute the bare erected cost (BEC). Cost estimation is limited to the simulated equipment that differs between the reference plant and the low-carbon configurations. The remaining equipment costs are considered fixed, subtracting the estimated costs of simulated units from the total plant cost in IEAGHG (2013). This fixed cost is then added to the CAPEX for each low-carbon configuration. Fans are classified as “sealed” when managing CO₂-rich streams. The cost estimation for preheating cyclones involves calculating the cyclone diameter (D_i), with distinct correlations for high- and standard-efficiency cyclones (De Lena et al., 2019). Only the two 1st-stage (top) cyclones are considered high efficiency, while all other cyclones are standard efficiency. For units such as the electrostatic precipitator (ESP), coal mill, and SNCR, where no suitable cost correlations were available in the literature, the “six-tenths rule” was applied, scaling based on a characteristic operating variable specific to each unit. The costs of the dehydration unit and knock-out drums in the CPU are neglected due to their expected low values and the complexity involved in cost estimation.

Cost estimation for the MEA capture unit applies a split-scaling approach, where 40% of the cost is based on the volumetric flowrate of inlet flue gas, while the remaining 60% is based on the captured CO₂ flowrate (NETL, 2019). Reference parameters vary between the RMP and GGHX configurations, as each has a different CO₂ inlet concentration, following cases simulated by Manzolini et al. (2015).

The BEC of an electrified entrainment calciner is derived by estimating the BEC of an entrainment calciner (De Lena et al., 2019), with an added cost for electrification of 100 €/kW_{th} (Quevedo Parra and Romano, 2023). In contrast, the cost for an electrified drop tube calciner is adapted from LEILAC2 (2023) and scaled according to the heat duty with a scaling exponent of 1, considering the modular nature of this technology.

Table S26. Cost correlations and installation factors for the various process units as a function of scaling parameters.

Process unit	Parameter	Correlation	Material	IF	Reference
Fan (non-sealed) ^a	$\dot{V}^{IN}(\text{m}^3/\text{h})$ $\dot{W}_{shaft}(\text{kW})$	$EC(\text{M}\text{€}_{2014}) = K_1 \left(\frac{\dot{V}}{\dot{V}_{ref}} \right)^{0.5} + K_2 \left(\frac{\dot{W}}{\dot{W}_{ref}} \right)^{0.65}$	-	1.4	De Lena et al. (2019)
Fan (sealed)	$\dot{V}^{IN}(\text{m}^3/\text{h})$ $\dot{W}_{shaft}(\text{kW})$	$EC(\text{M}\text{€}_{2014}) = 1.4 \cdot C_1 \left(\frac{\dot{V}}{\dot{V}_{ref}} \right)^{0.5} + C_2 \left(\frac{\dot{W}}{\dot{W}_{ref}} \right)^{0.65}$	-	1.4	De Lena et al. (2019)
Bag filter (including fan and conveyor)	$\dot{V}^{IN}(\text{m}^3/\text{h})$	$BEC(\text{M}\text{€}_{2018}) = 1.75 \cdot 10^{-3} (\dot{V})^{0.6} \frac{1}{1.14}$	-	Included	Magli et al. (2022)
Electrostatic precipitator	$\dot{V}^{IN}(\text{m}^3/\text{s})$	$EC(\text{M}\text{€}_{2014}) = 1.013 \left(\frac{\dot{V}}{107} \right)^{0.6}$	-	1.6	Gardarsdottir et al. (2019)
Cyclone	$\dot{V}^{IN}(\text{m}^3/\text{s})$	$D_i(\text{mm}) = 647 \dot{V}^{0.422}$ (high efficiency) $D_i(\text{mm}) = 1548 \dot{V}^{0.28}$ (std. efficiency) $EC(\text{M}\text{€}_{2014}) = 3.98 \cdot 10^{-9} (D_i)^2 + 2.73 \cdot 10^{-6} D_i + 0.016$	-	2.4	De Lena et al. (2019)
Entrainment calciner	$\dot{V}^{OUT}(\text{m}^3/\text{s})$	$EC(\text{M}\text{€}_{2014}) = 52.5 \cdot 10^{-3} (\dot{V})^{0.5}$	-	2.08	De Lena et al. (2019)
Coal Mill	$\dot{m}_{coal}(\text{kg}/\text{s})$	$EC(\text{M}\text{€}_{2013}) = 6.3 \left(\frac{\dot{m}}{2.93} \right)^{0.6}$	-	2.08	IEAGHG (2013)
SNCR	$\dot{m}_{coal}(\text{kg}/\text{s})$	$BEC(\text{M}\text{€}_{2014}) = 1.01 \left(\frac{\dot{m}}{3.87} \right)^{0.6}$	-	Included	Gardarsdottir et al. (2019)
Total cost cement plant	$\dot{m}_{clk}(\text{Mt}/\text{y})$	$BEC(\text{M}\text{€}_{2013}) = (145.5 - 13.1) \left(\frac{\dot{m}}{1} \right)^{0.6} + BEC_{Coal Mill} + BEC_{SNCR}$	-	Included	IEAGHG (2013)
Fixed cost cement plant	-	$BEC(\text{M}\text{€}_{2013}) = BEC_{Total Plant} - BEC_{Computed Units}$	-	Included	-
Centrifugal Compressor	$\dot{W}_{fluid}(\text{kW})$	$EC(\$_{2001}) = 10^{2.2897 + 1.3604 \log_{10}(\dot{W}) - 0.1027 [\log_{10}(\dot{W})]^2}$	SS	5.7	Turton et al. (2018)

Table S26. Cost correlations and installation factors for the various process units as a function of scaling parameters (continues from previous page).

Process unit	Parameter	Correlation	Material	IF	Reference
Drive	\dot{W}_{shaft} (kW)	$EC(\$_{2001}) = 10^{1.956+1.7142 \log_{10}(\dot{W})-0.2282[\log_{10}(\dot{W})]^2}$	-	1.5	Turton et al. (2018)
CO ₂ pump	\dot{W}_{shaft} (kW)	$EC(M\text{€}_{2011}) = 1.66 \left(\frac{\dot{W}}{1200} \right)^{0.85}$	CS	1.667	Cinti et al. (2018)
Plate&Frame heat exchanger	A_{exc} (m ²)	$EC(\$_{2001}) = 10^{4.6656-0.1557 \log_{10}(A)+0.1547[\log_{10}(A)]^2}$	SS	3.864	Turton et al. (2018)
Shell&Tube heat exchanger (fl. head)	A_{exc} (m ²)	$EC(\$_{2001}) = 10^{4.8306-0.8509 \log_{10}(A)+0.3187[\log_{10}(A)]^2}$	SS	4.618	Turton et al. (2018)
Evaporators	A_{exc} (m ²)	$EC(M\text{€}_{2017}) = 1.3 \left(\frac{A}{5000} \right)^{0.788}$	SS	3	Mastropasqua et al. (2019)
Heat pump	\dot{W}_{el} (kW)	$BEC(M\text{€}_{2018}) = 0.991 \cdot 10^{-3} \dot{W}$	-	Included	d'Amore et al. (2023)
MEA capture (RMP configuration)	$\dot{V}_{flue\ gas}$ (m ³ /s) $\dot{m}_{CO_2\ capt}$ (kg/s)	$EC(M\text{€}_{2013}) = 46.55 \left(0.4 \frac{\dot{V}}{844.3} + 0.6 \frac{\dot{m}}{143.9} \right)^{0.6}$	-	1.1	Manzolini et al. (2015) NETL (2019)
MEA capture (GGHX configuration)	$\dot{V}_{flue\ gas}$ (m ³ /s) $\dot{m}_{CO_2\ capt}$ (kg/s)	$EC(M\text{€}_{2013}) = 50.2 \left(0.4 \frac{\dot{V}}{1491.7} + 0.6 \frac{\dot{m}}{73.5} \right)^{0.6}$	-	1.1	Manzolini et al. (2015) NETL (2019)
Electrified Entrainment calciner	\dot{V}^{OUT} (m ³ /s) \dot{Q}_{th} (kW)	$BEC(M\text{€}_{2014}) = 2.08 \left(52.5 \cdot 10^{-3} (\dot{V})^{0.5} \right) + 100 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot \dot{Q}_{th}$	-	Included	De Lena et al. (2019) Quevedo Parra and Romano (2023)
Electrified Drop Tube calciner	\dot{Q}_{th} (kW)	$BEC(M\text{€}_{2023}) = 74.04 \left(\frac{\dot{Q}}{104\ 500} \right)^1$	-	Included	LEILAC2 (2023)

^a For reference volumetric flow rate $\dot{V}_{ref} = 25\ 000 - 380\ 000 - 485\ 000$ m³/h; $K_1 = 31.1 - 254.7 - 430.5$; for reference power $\dot{W}_{ref} = 75 - 1100 - 2000$ kW; $K_2 = 19.1 - 148.9 - 286.6$.

Process contingencies are assigned to each technology based on the process maturity and the level of detail in the equipment list, expressed as a factor of the *BEC* (Table S27).

Table S27. Process contingencies applied for different technologies.

Technology	Process contingency from maturity (% of <i>BEC</i>)	Process contingency from equipment list (% of <i>BEC</i>)	Reference
Electrified calciner	60	12	Quevedo Parra and Romano (2023)
CPU	20	12	Magli et al. (2022)
MEA PCC	15	3	Gardarsdottir et al. (2019)
Heat pump	20	3	Quevedo Parra and Romano (2023)
Heat exchangers	5	0	Gardarsdottir et al. (2019)

6. Cost of clinker sensitivity to the carbon tax

The cost of avoided CO₂ (*CAC*) reflects the carbon tax required to break even with the production costs of the reference plant without mitigation measures (i.e., with unabated CO₂ emissions). This is represented in the sensitivity analysis of the cost of clinker (*COC*) to carbon tax shown in Figure S16. The intersection point of the *COC* for the reference plant and the low-carbon alternatives corresponds to a carbon tax equal to the *CAC* values presented in Figure 10 of the main text. In Figure S16, the reference plant exhibits a steeper slope for its higher direct emissions. Conversely, the low-carbon scenarios demonstrate milder sensitivity to the carbon tax, driven more by the carbon intensity of the supplied electricity than by direct emissions. Among the low-carbon configurations, Ent-RMP consistently appears the most economically favourable across the range of carbon tax variations, while the others show similar overlapped results.

Figure S16. Cost of clinker sensitivity to the carbon tax for the reference plant and the low-carbon designs. DT-RMP = drop tube calciner with pure CO₂ preheating raw meal; Ent-RMP = entrainment calciner with pure CO₂ preheating raw meal; DT-GGHX = drop tube calciner with pure CO₂ preheating vent air via a gas-gas heat exchanger; Ent-GGHX = entrainment calciner with pure CO₂ preheating vent air via a gas-gas heat exchanger.

Nomenclature

Acronyms

BF	Bag Filter
CAPEX	Capital cost
CPU	Compression and Purification Unit
DAF	Dry ash-free
DEHYD	Dehydration step
DT	Drop tube
ESP	Electrostatic precipitator
Ent	Entrainment
FC	Fixed carbon
GGHX	Gas-gas heat exchanger configuration
HHV	Higher heating value
INTERC	Intercooler
LMTD	Logarithmic mean temperature difference
M	Moisture
MEA	Monoethanolamine
PCC	Post-combustion carbon capture
RMP	Raw meal preheating configuration
SNCR	Selective non-catalytic reduction
VM	Volatile matter

Symbols

a	–	Pressure drop coefficient
A_{exc}	m^2	Heat transfer area of heat exchanger
A^{IN}	m^2	Inlet cross-sectional area of cyclone
Ash	kg/kg_{ash}	Ash composition
BEC	€	Bare erected cost
CAC	€/t _{CO₂}	Cost of avoided CO ₂
C	–	Coefficient for the heat capacity polynomial expression
COC	€/t _{clk}	Cost of clinker
c_p	J/(mol · K)	Heat capacity
D	mm	Cyclone diameter
EC	€	Equipment cost
FA^{IN}	% kg _{FA} /kg _{clk}	False air ingress
H	kJ/kg	Mass enthalpy
H_f^o	J/mol	Mass enthalpy of formation in standard conditions
IF	–	Installation factor

K	–	Parameter for cost estimation of fan
\dot{m}	kg/s	Mass flowrate
MR	%	Residual moisture
MW	kg/kmol	Molar weight
OS	%	Raw mill oversize factor
p	bar	Absolute pressure
P	–	Coefficient for coal heat capacity polynomial expression
PA^{IN}	kg _{PA} /kg _{clk}	Primary air inlet
PXA	kg/kg _{dry fuel} kg/kg _{wet fuel}	Proximate analysis mass fraction
\dot{Q}_D	kW	Decomposition heat
T	K	Temperature
TA^{IN}	kg _{TA} /kg _{clk}	Transport air inlet
U_{exc}	W/(m ² · K)	Heat transfer coefficient of heat exchanger
UA	kg/kg _{dry fuel}	Ultimate analysis mass fraction
v	m/s	Velocity
\dot{V}	m ³ /s	Volumetric flowrate
VF	–	Vapor fraction
w	–	Mass fraction
\dot{W}_{fluid}	kW	Power delivered to the fluid
\dot{W}_{shaft}	kW	Shaft power

Greek letters

ρ_{MIX}	kg/m ³	Gas-solid mixture mass density
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Sub-/Superscripts

clk	Clinker
COMB	Related to dry ash-free fuel complete combustion
D	Related to decomposition species
el	Electric
FA	False air
fuel	Fuel
G	Gas stream
IN	Inlet stream
OUT	Outlet stream
PROD	Product
REACT	Reactant
S	Solid stream
th	Thermal
TOT	Total in the system

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